

- - -

2010/12/22

2011/05/02

54

2009 /10/1 - 2008 /08 /01

Pseudomonas aeruginosa

Staphylococcus aureus

(%55.5)
(15 - 1)

%48.10

(%44.4)

%31.37

(30 - 15)

.(60 - 30)

%23.5

(%100)

%58

(%85)

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Bacteria associated with Ear Infections in the National Hospital in Qamishly- Syria and their Antimicrobial Resistance

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ABSTRACT

54 isolates were isolated of the bacteria associated with ear infections which have antimicrobial resistance from the patients in the National Hospital in Qamishly City during the period from 01/08/2008 to 31/10/ 2009. The number of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was high, followed by *Staphylococcus aureus*. It has been found that the rate of ear infections was lower in male (44.4%) than female (55.5%), and was (48.10%) in the first age category (1- 15 year) more than the second age category (15- 30 year) (31.37%), while the rate of ear infections was (23.5%) in the third age category(30- 60 year).

We found that all the strains of isolated bacteria showed high susceptibility to Imipenem (100%), and all bacteria of *Pseudomonas*, *klebsella*, *Proteus*, *Enterobacter*, showed high sensitivity to ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin (85%), but only staphylococcus (58%).

In addition, most isolated bacteria showed intermediate sensitivity to tobramicine, amikacine, gentamycine, and cephalosporins like ceftazidime, cefaclor and cefotaxime.

At the same time, most isolated bacteria showed resistance to Amoxicilline, Ampicillin, Penicillin, Oxacylline, Sulphamethoxazole, erythromycin, vancomycine and tetracyclines.

Key Words: Bacteria, Resistance, Antibiotics, Ear, National Hospital in Qamishly

:
Enterobacter *Escherichia coli*
Pseudomonas *Proteus* *Klebsiella*
2000) *Staphylococcus* (2007
(Jawetz *et al.*, 1989)
(Fauci *et al.*, 2008)
(Henry 2001)
)
.(Gladwin and Trattler 2000 2000

:
)
(Fauci *et al.*, 2008 1987

Fauci *et al.*, 1987)
Pseudomonas aeruginosa .(2008
Staphylococcus aureus
Roland *et al.*, 1995,)
.(Lalwani 2006, Fauci *et al.*, 2008
Plasmids (DNA)

(Storz & Aronis 2000, Wickens & Wade 2005)

40

.(Blaser *et al.*, 1995)

(2002)

(2006)

.(1999)

(Livrelli *et al.*, 1996)

:

(2004)

(Brook &)

Gober 2005

:

(Rashid *et al.*, 2007)

Lo *et*)

(*al.*2010

(Aydemir *et al.*, 2010)

12-1

(Shamsuddeen *et al.*, 2010)

(1999)

(1999)

(2003)

%58.8

(2010) (2005) (2005)

.1
.2
.3

Autoclave () : .1

Laminar Flow

Hi Nutrient Agar : **Culture Media** .2
 Eosin Methylene Blue Agar media
 Biomark Cetrimide Agar Criterion
 Kligler Biomark Mueller Hinton Agar
 Hi Urea Agar base Biomark iron Agar
 Hi media Simmons citrate media
 Criterion Mannitol Salt Agar
 Criterion Peptone water Agar
 .3

Amoxicilline	Ax 25 mcg	Amoxicillin\clavolanic acid	AMC30mcg
Ampicillin	AM10mcg	Cefaclor	CEC30mcg
Cefoxitin	FOX30mcg	Ceftazidime	CAZ30mcg
Cefuroxim Sodium	CXM30mcg	Cefazoline	CZ 30 mcg
Ciprofloxacin	CIP 5 mcg	Imipenem	IPM 10mcg
Amikacine	AK30mcg	Cefotaxime	CX30mcg
Ofloxacin	OFX5mcg	Sulphamethoxazol	SXT25mcg
Gentamycine	GM 10mcg	Tobramicine	Tob 10mcg
Pefloxacin	PE5mcg	Levofloxacin	LEV 5 mcg
Oxacillin	OX 1mcg	Penicillin G	P 10mcg
Vancomycine	VA 30mcg	Erythromycin	E 15 mcg
Tetracycline	TE 30mcg		

2009/10/1 2008/8/1
Swab

:Specimen culture .1

:Identification of Bacteria .2
:(Henry 2001 2003 2001)

.3

() EMB

Cetrimide

Agar base

Pseudomonas aeruginosa

Kirby : .3
National Committee for Clinical Laboratory bauer

(NCCLS) Standard

(mcg)

Resistant (Henry 2001 2003 Intermediate 2001 Sensitive)

35

24-18

.(2003)

()

Mc farland

99.5 %1.17)⁸10×1.5 Ba Cl₂. 2H₂O Mc farland 0.5 0.5 (%1

:

5 - 3

2 - 1.5

) 24 - 18 35

.(Henry 2001 2001

SPSS

: .4

.One Way Anova

0.05

Spearman

(1)

(1)

%		Bacteria
57.4	31	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
24.07	13	<i>S. aureus</i>
9.25	5	<i>Klebsiellae sp.</i>
7.4	4	<i>Proteae sp.</i>
1.85	1	<i>Enterobacter sp.</i>
100	54	Total No.

1

(%7.4) (%9.25) (%24.07) (%57.4)

(%1.85)

(2005)

: %11.8 %23.5 %58.8

(2003)

(Rashid *et al.*, 2007)

(Shamsuddeen *et al.*, 2010)

.(2004) %10 %17

.1

%55.5 (%44.4)

.(2) 0.169

(2)

%	No.	Sex
44.4	24	Male
55.5	30	Female
100	54	Total No.

.2

%48.10 (15-1)

%31.37 (30-15)

%23.5 (60-30)

(3) 0.097-

(2004) :

(Aydemir *et al.*, 2010)

.(Shamsuddeen *et al.*, 2010)

(3)

%	No.	Age
48.10	26	1 - 15
31.37	16	15 - 30
23.52	12	30 - 60
100	54	Total No.

(4-1)

Pseudomonas aeruginosa

.1

(1) 4 :

%100

%62.06

%68.9

%89.8

%20.86

%31.03

%13.79

%34.48

%44.8

G

Pseudomonas aeruginosa

(1)

...

Staphylococcus aureus

.2

(2)

4

Staphylococcus aureus

%75

%100

%50

%58.3

%25

%41.6

%33.3

%.8.3

Staphylococcus

(2)

aureus

Klebsiella

.3

%100

Klebsiella

%60

%40

%80

%80

%60

%60

%80

%20

%40

%20

G

:

.(3 4)

Klebsiella

(3)

Proteus

.4

%50

%100

Proteus

%25

%50

%75

%25

%25

G

(4 4)

Proteus

(4)

Enterobacter

.5

%100
%100

Enterobacter

%100

G
(.4)

(4)

Antibiotics mcg	<i>Pseudomonas</i>		<i>Staphylococcus</i>		<i>Klebseilla</i>		<i>Proteus</i>		<i>Enterobacter</i>	
	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.
AMC 30	0	31	50	13	0	5	0	4	0	1
LEV 5	68.9	31	58.3	13	80	5	75	4	100	1
CIP 5	89.6	31	58.3	13	60	5	75	4	100	1
PE 5	34.4	31	41.6	13	20	5	75	4	0	1
OFX 5	13.7	31	8.33	13	20	5	0	4	0	1
GM 10	20.6	31	50	13	40	5	50	4	100	1
TOB 10	62.1	31	25	13	60	5	25	4	100	1
AK 30	31.1	31	50	13	80	5	50	4	0	1
VA 30	0	31	25	13	0	5	0	4	0	1
CXM 30	0	31	41.6	13	20	5	0	4	0	1
CX 30	10.3	31	33.3	13	20	5	0	4	0	1
CAZ 30	44.8	31	25	13	20	5	0	4	0	1
FOX 30	0	31	8.33	13	0	5	0	4	0	1
CEC 30	0	31	75	13	40	5	25	4	0	1
CZ 30	0	31	75	13	80	5	0	4	0	1
IPM 10	100	31	100	13	100	5	100	4	100	1
SXT 25	0	31	41.6	13	0	5	25	4	0	1
P G 10	0	31	0	13	0	5	0	4	0	1
AX 25	0	31	0	13	0	5	0	4	0	1
AM 10	0	31	33.3	13	0	5	0	4	0	1
OX 10	0	31	33.3	13	0	5	0	4	0	1
TE 30	0	31	8.33	13	0	5	0	4	0	1
E 15	0	31	25	13	0	5	0	4	0	1

()

.0.02 0.05

(5)

.(Rashid *et al.*, 2007 2005)

Antibiotics mcg	<i>Pseudomonas</i>			<i>Staphylococcus</i>	
	%	2005	Rashid <i>et al.</i>		2005
AMC 30	0			%50	%50
LEV 5	68.9			%58.3	
CIP 5	89.6	%80	%13.3	%58.3	%85
PE 5	34.4			%41.6	
OFX 5	13.7			%8.33	
GM 10	20.6	%88	%63.5	%50	%72
TOB 10	62.1			%25	
AK 30	31.1	%88	%9.7	%50	
VA 30	0			%25	%100
CXM 30	0			%41.6	
CX 30	10.3	0		%33.3	
CAZ 30	44.8	%85	%48.3	%25	
FOX 30	0			%8.33	
CEC 30	0			%75	
CZ 30	0			%75	
IPM 10	100	%82		%100	
SXT 25	0			%41.6	%86
P G 10	0			0	
AX 25	0			0	
AM 10	0			%33.3	%5
OX 10	0			%33.3	
TE 30	0			%8.33	
E 15	0			%25	%46

)

(2003

...

	2005	(2004)	
%88			(5)
%31.03			
%85	%82	%80	%20.6
.	%44.8	%100 %89.09	
(5)			
	%50		
%72	%86	%5	
%33.3		%85	%100
	.	%58.3 %25 %50	%41.6
(5)			
	(Rashid <i>et al.</i> , 2007)		
%63.5	%13.3		
%89.6		%48.3	%9.7
	.	%44.8 %31.03	%20.6
			.1
			.2
			.3
			.4

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